

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

Articles for publication in the *International Rice Research Newsletter* (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha, 2 h/d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) or g/row.
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min, \$2, 3 kg/ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N; 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names — not trade names — for chemicals.
- The US\$ is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters: Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization OVERALL PROGRESS

IRAT170: a high-yielding, medium-duration upland rice for Nigeria

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We tested a number of breeding lines and varieties in 1983 upland rice zonal trials. IRAT170 was identified as a high-yielding variety with medium maturity and good plant type. It was evaluated with other selected entries in the advanced yield nurseries of the Coordinated Rice Evaluation Trials (CRET) in 1984 and 1985. In 1984 CRET, IRAT170 outyielded the commonly cultivated popular variety FARO 11 in four of the five locations.

In 1985, IRAT170 was superior to FARO 11 in all four locations (see table). Grain yield of IRAT170 was 37% higher than that of FARO 11.

IRAT170, a cross of IRAT13 and Palawan, was introduced from the Ivory Coast. It is medium tall (120 cm) with medium maturity (125 d). It has straight compact tillers and is resistant to lodging. Panicles are also compact with good spikelet fertility. Grains are long bold (B type) with nonglutinous endosperm. Cooking quality is better (amylose content 23.0%) than that of FARO 11 (amylose content 19.0%). It is also superior to FARO 11 in pest and disease resistance.

IRAT170 has been recommended for release for upland humid areas of Nigeria. □

Yield performance of IRAT170 in multilocal trials, Nigeria, 1984-85.

Location	Grain yield (t/ha)						Increase over check (%)
	1984		1985		Mean		
	IRAT170	FARO 11	IRAT170	FARO 11	IRAT170	FARO 11	
Moor Plantation	3.6	3.4	5.6	3.7	4.6	3.6	28
IITA, Ibadan	1.4	0.6	0.6	0.1	1.0	0.4	150
Ikenne	2.6	2.1	2.6	1.9	2.6	2.0	30
Amakama	2.1	2.2	2.4	1.8	2.3	2.0	15
Oonne	2.7	1.7	—	—	2.7	1.7	59
Mean	2.4	2.0	2.8	1.9	2.6	1.9	37

Development of a rice composite for Nigeria

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Six rice varieties with similar agronomic characteristics but different reactions to diseases, lodging, and drought were selected and diallel-crossed in 1977. The varieties were commonly cultivated FARO 11, drought-tolerant E425 and OS4, FARO 25 with moderate resistance to brown spot, and high-yielding

IRAT1069m-1-2 and IR1154-243-1. The F₁ and F₂ populations were phenotypically similar to the parents except for variations in height and tolerance for drought and diseases. The F₂ crosses tested in 1978 were grouped into five classes (Table 1). These groups, with FARO 11 and a physical mixture of the six parent varieties as checks, were tested for 3 yr.

FAROX299, involving crosses of IRAT1069m-1-2 with other varieties, was shorter than FARO 11 and other crosses. It also showed higher